

Title: Extreme heat and mortality in the Niakhar area

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INTRODUCTION:

Climate change affects all countries around the world and debates on this subject have become increasingly important in the last decade, notably with the Paris Climate Accord, the first universal climate agreement. This interest is motivated by all the impacts that can result from this phenomenon, particularly on human health.

AIM:

To analyze the relationship between heat and mortality in the Sahelo-Sudanese zone precisely at Niakhar.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

To take into account a possible non-linearity of the temperature-mortality relationship and thus to detect thermal optima, a GAM was estimated on the data. Finally, in order to measure the impact of heat waves, temperature and other climatic variables on deaths and forecast weather-related mortality, estimates were made using ARIMAX modeling.

RESULTS:

The results indicated, considering the temperature, rain, wind speed and visibility, few thresholds of minimum mortality. However, an increase in deaths due to rising temperatures and the presence of rain and a decrease in deaths due to increased visibility are noted as well as a fairly acceptable prediction of mortality.

CONCLUSIONS:

These results serve as a basis of reflection for the public authorities, in order to set up an alert platform based on weather forecasts of temperature evolution.

KEYWORDS:

Climate change, apparent temperature, heat waves, mortality, LOESS, ARIMAX, GAM, Niakhar

BIOGRAPHY:

Mr NIANG has completed his ingeener degree at the age of 22 years from Ecole Nationale de la Statistique et de l'Analyse de l'Information of Dakar, Senegal. He is performing a specialization at the Ecole Nationale de la Statistique et de l'Analyse de l'Information of Rennes, France.